

Comparative experimental study of the post-fire behaviour of mild, high-strength and ultra-high-strength steel

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ABSTRACT

A thorough understanding and realistic modelling of material behaviour is essential for a safe and reliable assessment of the remaining load-bearing capacity of steel components after a fire. However, there is still a lack of comprehensive experimental studies on the post-fire material behaviour of high-strength steels, so the high-strength steel components are usually removed after a fire. This paper presents the results of an extensive experimental study of the post-fire behaviour of two quenched and tempered high-strength steels S690QL and S960QL, and a comparison to a mild steel S355J2+N. Tensile tests were carried out on small-scale specimens after heating to elevated temperatures and a cooling phase to ambient temperature. The material behaviour of the steels was compared by analysing the resulting stress-strain relationships from the tests, including strength and stiffness properties. Additionally, the influence of full temperature cycles on the microstructure of the steels and the differences between the material behaviour of mild steels and quenched and tempered high-strength steels were investigated using micrographs of the specimens. Thus, the paper provides the basis for a phenomenological description of the material behaviour of high-strength steels after fire for advanced modelling applications.

Keywords: High-strength Steels, Material Characterisation, Structural Fire Behaviour, Post-fire Behaviour

1 INTRODUCTION

Responsible use of primary resources is a key aspect of ensuring sustainable development in line with the UN's SDGs (1) at an economic, social, and ecological level. In this context, the use of high-strength structural steels and the opportunities this opens up for material savings are of great importance. In addition, building structures and infrastructures should be used for as long as possible, or reclaimed steel components should be reused in a new structural context. For the continued use and possible reuse of components exposed to fire due to possible thermal damage, the question arises as to whether visually undamaged building components can continue to be used. An important prerequisite for this decision is sound knowledge about possible changes in material properties such as strength and stiffness due to effects of fire and elevated temperatures. In the case of mild steels, it is generally assumed that the post-fire material behaviour is completely reversible and that a component can continue to be used if there is no significant deformation. This assumption is based on several studies on the mechanical material behaviour of mild steels after a fire (2-7).

However, in the case of high-strength steels, especially quenched and tempered structural steel, there are doubts in this respect and it can be assumed that the mechanical material behaviour changes due to high temperatures, which is why components made of high-strength steels are usually replaced after a fire event. However, there is still a lack of experimentally verified findings on the extent of the impact of elevated temperatures on the post-fire behaviour of high-strength steels. This paper presents a comprehensive experimental study on the mechanical material behaviour of high- and

ultra-high-strength quenched and tempered steels of grades S690QL and S960QL after an exposure to elevated temperatures taking into consideration the stress-strain response, mechanical material properties such as strength and stiffness as well as the analysis of micrographs of the microstructure. The results of our tests are supplemented by comparisons with findings from literature (2-19). The study therefore provides the basis for a phenomenological description of the material behaviour of high-strength steels after fire for advanced modelling applications. The long-term objective is to demonstrate the possibilities for the further use of high-strength steel components after a fire in order to save valuable resources.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

The test program of the study consisted of post-fire tensile tests on small-scale specimens made from two quenched and tempered high-strength steels of grades S690QL and S960QL and, in addition, of a normalised mild steel of grade S355J2+N. In the case of the high-strength steels, the specimens were taken from plate material with an initial thickness of 12 mm, and in the case of the mild steel flange plates of a hot-rolled HEA100 profile were taken as source material. The specimens were manufactured each from the core material of the plates and had a dog-bone shape with a constant thickness of 6 mm. The geometry of the specimens is shown in Fig. 1(c).

For each test, a specimen was installed in the combined test setup consisting of a universal testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 250 kN and an electric furnace with three independently controllable heating zones with a maximum temperature of 1200°C for each zone. The test setup is presented schematically in Fig. 1(a).

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic illustration and (b) photograph of the test setup and (c) geometry of the specimens.

The first step of the tests consisted of five loading- and unloading cycles in the elastic range with a maximum force corresponding to $0.8 \cdot f_{y, \text{nom}}$ at ambient temperature to ensure the centric alignment of the specimen in the test setup and to determine the Young's modulus at ambient temperature.

Next, the specimen was heated to a defined maximum temperature T_u with a constant heating rate of 15 K/min while a small tensile force of $F_{\text{hold}} = 500$ N was applied. The heating of the furnace was controlled with three mantle-thermocouples, which were placed directly on the specimen's surface. Three additional mantle-thermocouples were used to measure the air temperature inside the furnace simultaneously. When the pre-defined maximum temperature T_u was reached, the temperature was kept constant for 30 min to ensure the uniform heating of the specimen. Values of $T_u = 400, 550, 700,$ and 900°C were chosen as the pre-defined maximum temperatures. After the soaking time, the heating

device of the furnace was switched off, and the specimen was left to cool inside the furnace under natural ventilation conditions without any additional cooling device. When the specimen was cooled completely to ambient temperature, a tensile test was conducted in a strain-rate-controlled manner with a constant strain rate of 1 %/min. The measurement of the elongation of the specimens and the respective conversion to strain values during the tensile tests was done with a high-temperature extensometer. A photograph of the extensometer with the ceramic rods placed on the surface of a specimen is shown in Fig. 1(b). The measured elongation of the specimens also served as a feedback variable for a closed-loop-feedback-control of the testing machine during the strain-rate-controlled tests.

3 TEST RESULTS

3.1 Initial Material Behaviour

Reference tests at ambient temperature were conducted for the mild steel S355J2+N and the high-strength steels S690QL and S960QL to determine the initial material behaviour at ambient temperature. The results of these tests served as a reference for the material behaviour after the exposure to elevated temperatures. The resulting stress-strain-responses are presented in Fig. 2(a) and (b). In addition, the fracture surface and micrographs of the microstructure are shown in Fig. 2(c).

The initial stress-strain-response of the investigated steel S355J2+N in Fig. 2(a) and (b) shows the characteristic shape of structural steel with a linear-elastic increase in the range of small strains with a slope of $E = 212316 \text{ N/mm}^2$, followed by a distinct yield plateau. The suffix N of the material indicates that it was initially normalised during the manufacturing process. In general, the normalising of steel consists of a heating process of the material over the recrystallisation temperature and a subsequent air cooling to ambient temperature. Through the normalising process, the strength is increased, and the internal stresses of the material are reduced during the heating; further, as a result of the slow cooling, the ductility of the material is increased and the microstructure of the steel becomes more uniform and refined. The normalised steel S355J2+N of the present study showed an actual yield strength of $f_y = 423 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Further, a hardening up to the tensile strength of $f_t = 554 \text{ N/mm}^2$ was recorded leading to a yield strength ratio of $f_y/f_t = 0.76$. The micrograph of the material in Fig. 2(c) shows that the microstructure has a grid pattern with mostly uniform grain sizes. The investigated high-strength steels S690QL and S960QL were initially water-quenched and tempered according to EN 10025-6 (20). The manufacturing process of quenching and tempering is used to gain fine-grained steels with high hardness or strength values. Within the thermal treatment, the material is heated above the recrystallisation temperature, so that the initial coarse-grained microstructure of the steel, which consisted mostly of cubic body-centred ferrite and perlite phases transforms into a structure that consists mostly of cubic face-centred austenite phases. Subsequently, the material is cooled rapidly below the γ - α -transformation temperature with the help of additional cooling mediums like oil or water. Through the rapid cooling, the carbon precipitation is hampered so that the recovery of the ferrite and perlite phases is prevented and the austenitic microstructure remains. This results in a fine-grained microstructure with very high hardness and strength values depending on the cooling velocity. The subsequent tempering process is carried out to increase the ductility of the material. Thereby the steel is re-heated to moderate temperatures and cooled down slowly. During this tempering process, the carbon atoms partly diffuse out. Accordingly, the fine-grained microstructure partly changes and the hardness and strength slightly decrease, but the toughness of the material is increased significantly and compared to the initial material before quenching, the resulting material has improved strength and hardness values.

In Fig. 2(a) and (b), the stress-strain-response of the quenched and tempered high-strength steels S690QL and S960QL are presented. The curves of both investigated materials have a linear-elastic increase in the beginning for small strains. The slopes in this range are $E_{1.0\%/min} = 204764 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (S690QL) and $E_{1.0\%/min} = 190855 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (S960QL). Further, both materials have a distinct yield plateau with yield strength values of $f_{y,1.0\%/min} = 786 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (S690QL) and $f_{y,1.0\%/min} = 1041 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (S960QL), which – like in case of the mild steel – reveals overstrength of the materials. The yield

plateaus of the high-strength steels are followed by a hardening range up to the tensile strengths of $f_{t,1.0\%/min} = 794 \text{ N/mm}^2$ in case of the steel S690QL and $f_{t,1.0\%/min} = 1068 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the steel S960QL. The yield strength ratios of the high-strength steels are higher than the value of the investigated mild steel with $f_y/f_t = 0.99$ for S690QL and $f_y/f_t = 0.97$ for S960QL. Fig. 2(b) proves that the deformation capacity of the steels S690QL and S960QL is lower than the one of the steel of grade S355J2+N. To investigate the influence of the strain rate on the material behaviour of the high-strength steels, tests with two different strain rates of $d\varepsilon/dt = 0.2 \text{ \%/min}$ and $d\varepsilon/dt = 1.0 \text{ \%/min}$ were conducted and the results are presented in Fig. 2(a) and (b). The stress-strain-curves from tests with different strain rates are almost congruent up to the maximum measured strength values, which reveals that the strain rate has a negligible effect on the material behaviour at ambient temperature.

The micrographs of the quenched and tempered steels in Fig. 2(c) show a similar microstructure. The microstructures are – as expected - fine grained with uniform grain sizes.

Fig. 2 Initial material behaviour of the investigated steels S355J2+N, S690QL and S960QL at ambient temperature in the form of stress-strain-curves in the strain range (a) up to $\varepsilon_{tot} = 2.0 \text{ \%}$ and (b) $\varepsilon_{tot} = 20 \text{ \%}$ and (c) photographs of the fracture surfaces of the specimens and micrographs.

3.2 Post-Fire Stress-Strain-Response

Fig. 3 shows the stress-strain curves, which were obtained from post-fire tests on the investigated materials in the strain range up to $\varepsilon_{tot} = 2.0 \text{ \%}$ (Fig. 3(a)) and up to $\varepsilon_{tot} = 20 \text{ \%}$ (Fig. 3(b)). The colouring of the curves indicates the respective maximum temperatures T_u of the heating process of the tests.

All post-fire stress-strain curves of the three materials have the characteristic shape of structural steels with linear-elastic increase and a distinct yield plateau. Further, all curves almost coincide in the beginning of the tests, which leads to the hypothesis that the linear-elastic stiffnesses of the materials are fully reversible after an exposure to high temperatures.

However, there are some differences between the mild steels and the high-strength steels in case of the strength recovery. In case of the mild steel S355J2+N the yield strength and ultimate strength are almost completely reversible, as the curves from the post-fire tests after heating to the various elevated temperatures coincide to the initial curve at ambient temperature (Fig. 3(b)). Only in case of very high maximum temperatures of $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$ significant strength losses occur after the cooling. The respective stress-strain curve is lower compared to the other curves of material S355J2+N. In case of the high-strength materials, the post-fire strength strongly depends on the maximum temperature of the heating phase. Up to a maximum temperature of $T_u = 550^\circ\text{C}$, the material behaviour in Fig. 3— like in case of the mild steel - is reversible. Higher maximum temperatures, however, lead to significant strength losses in the post-fire tests. After an exposure to $T_u = 700^\circ\text{C}$ the resulting stress-strain-curves from post-fire tests on S690QL and S960QL are significantly lower than the initial curves at ambient temperature.

After an exposure to the very high maximum temperature of $T_u=900^\circ\text{C}$ the absolute values of the yield strength of the mild steel S355J2+N and of the quenched and tempered high-strength steels S690QL and S960QL are of the same order of magnitude. For S355J2+N the 0.2 %-proof strength is $f_{y,0.2}=319\text{ N/mm}^2$, for S690QL it is $f_{y,0.2}=272.4\text{ N/mm}^2$ and for S960QL a value of $f_{y,0.2}=354.1\text{ N/mm}^2$ was measured. Therefore, all of the strength values are within the range of common mild steels. It is assumed that this is caused by phase changes in the microstructure of the initially quenched and tempered materials due to the exceeding of the A_1 -phase-change-temperature in tests with $T_u=900^\circ\text{C}$. The exposure to very high temperatures reversed the quenching and tempering process so that the fine-grained microstructure is turned into a coarser grained structure, which leads to lower strength values. Micrographs of the specimens prove this assumption (see section 3.5).

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves of the materials S355J2+N, S690QL and S960QL under post-fire conditions in the strain ranges (a) up to $\epsilon_{\text{tot}}=2.0\%$ and (b) up to $\epsilon_{\text{tot}}=20\%$.

3.3 Post-Fire Material Properties

From the stress-strain curves in Fig. 3, material properties were determined and summarised in Tab. 1. The table includes the strength values $f_{y,0.5}$, $f_{y,1.5}$ and $f_{y,2.0}$, which represent the measured stresses at the points of total strains of 0.5, 1.5 and 2.0 %. Additionally, the 0.2 %-proof-strength $f_{y,0.2}$ was determined with an offset-method referring to the Young's modulus E . The values of the Young's modulus E were determined as the slope in the linear elastic range between $0.1 \cdot f_{y,2.0}$ and $0.3 \cdot f_{y,2.0}$. Further, the proportional limit f_p was defined as the measured stress value when the measured strain value differs 2 % from the ideal linear straight line in the beginning of the test and the tensile strength f_t was determined as the maximum measured stress value during the tensile test. The elastic fracture strain ϵ_u was derived at the point of the fracture of the specimen using an offset-method related to the Young's modulus of the beginning of the test.

The material properties in Tab. 1 from post-fire tests ($T_u > 20^\circ\text{C}$) were related to the respective initial values from reference tests at ambient temperature (20°C) and the resulting ratios $X_{\text{pf}}/X_{20^\circ\text{C}}$ were plotted over the maximum temperatures of the post-fire tests to get reduction factor-temperature-relationships. In Fig. 4, the reduction factor-temperature-relationships for the material properties (a) Young's modulus E , (b) effective yield strength at 2.0 % total strain $f_{y,2.0}$ and 0.2 %-proof strength $f_{y,0.2}$, (c) tensile strength f_t and (d) the ratio of yield strength (0.2 %-proof-strength) and tensile strength f_y/f_t from post-fire tests on S355J2+N, S690QL and S960QL are presented. The colours of the curves thereby indicate the investigated materials. Orange curves are assigned to material S355J2+N, blue curves to S690QL and green curves belong to material S960QL. In addition, Fig. 4

includes respective values from literature regarding the post-fire behaviour of mild steels with a nominal yield strength up to $f_{y,nom} \leq 460 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (orange points), high-strength steels up to $f_{y,nom} \leq 700 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (blue points) and ultra-high-strength steels with $f_{y,nom} \leq 960 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (green points) and $f_{y,nom} > 960 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (grey points). The values from literature were used for a comparative study in section 3.4.

Tab. 1 Material properties from post-fire tests.

	T_u [°C]	E [N/mm ²]	f_p [N/mm ²]	$f_{y,0.2}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{y,0.5}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{y,1.5}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{y,2.0}$ [N/mm ²]	f_t [N/mm ²]	ϵ_u [%]
S355J2+N	20	212316	390.2	423	425.2	442.1	457.4	553.6	27.6
	400	222352	467	429.1	431.7	443	453.2	547.9	24
	550	221985	446.6	421.5	419	414.3	428.2	539.5	26.6
	700	219464	357.3	383.4	380	378.7	385.4	496.8	29.2
	900	200976	252.8	319	312.5	313.1	312.5	439.8	33.9
S690QL	20	204764	786	763.4	759.5	760.3	760	794.4	16.7
	400	213736	717	742.5	744.2	752.7	755.5	783.4	14.2
	550	214417	744.7	737.9	739.6	736.1	737.2	775.7	16.1
	700	216825	575.6	537.3	536.3	538.5	537.5	607.7	21.7
	900	197603	313.8	272.4	274.7	273.4	283.4	430.4	32.4
S960QL	20	190855	1041.4	1029.9	1003	1035.5	1038.6	1067.8	14.4
	400	218929	1045.6	1039.5	1055.2	1046.4	1049.7	1078.6	14.6
	550	206523	1040.6	1027.5	1033.4	1034.9	1039	1069.6	14.1
	700	215341	814.1	785.6	786.4	783.3	783	834.5	16.5
	900	196032	349.3	354.1	356	398.2	407.2	545.5	23.7

Fig. 4(a) proves the hypothesis that the stiffness recovery of all the investigated materials of the present study is almost independent from the achieved maximum temperature of the heating phase of the tests. The reduction factor-temperature-relationships of the Young's modulus are almost 1.0 or even higher for all maximum temperatures, which means there is a full recovery of the initial stiffness. The graphs in Fig. 4(b) and (c) show that the recovery of the strength values of the investigated high-strength materials S690QL and S960QL is strongly dependent on the maximum temperature of the heating phase. Up to a maximum temperature of $T_u = 550^\circ\text{C}$ the initial values of the yield strength (Fig. 4(b)) as well as the tensile strength (Fig. 4(c)) were achieved in the post-fire tests, as the reduction factor- temperature-relationships reach values to about 1.0. However, higher maximum temperatures of $T_u = 700^\circ\text{C}$ or $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$ lead to degradations of the strength values in the post-fire range so that after temperature exposure to $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$ only about 40 % of the initial yield strengths (Fig. 4(b)) and 50 % of the tensile strengths (Fig. 4(c)) of the high-strength steels recovered. In the case of the investigated mild steel S355J2+N, this effect is less pronounced. After an exposure to $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$, about 70% of the initial yield strength and 80% of the initial tensile strength recovered. In Fig. 4(d), the ratio of the 0.2 %-proof-strength and the tensile strength from post-fire tests is plotted over the maximum temperature of the respective tests. For all the investigated materials of the present study, the ratio is almost independent from the maximum temperature up to $T_u = 700^\circ\text{C}$. In addition, the ratio is similar for both quenched and tempered high-strength steels with values within the range about 0.97. Further, the values of the high-strength materials are higher than the ones of mild steel S355J2+N in the range of 0.78.

After an exposure to $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$, however, the ratio $f_{y,pf}/f_{t,pf}$ of the high-strength steels is significantly reduced compared to the initial value from reference tests at ambient temperature and even lower than the one of the mild steel S355J2+N, which is still almost the same compared to ambient temperature. Very high maximum-temperatures therefore affect the yield strength ratio of quenched and tempered high-strength steels. The austenitic microstructure, which was achieved through the

initial quenching and tempering process and causes higher strengths and less ductility of the materials is changed when the A_1 -phase-change-temperature is exceeded in the tests. Due to the slow cooling in the present tests, carbon precipitation can take place in an unimpeded manner, which leads to a changed microstructure with higher amounts of ferrite and perlite phases in the post-fire test specimens. This results in materials with lower strength values but higher ductility compared to the initial high-strength steels.

Fig. 4 Reduction factor-temperature relationships for (a) the Young's modulus E , (b) the effective yield strength at 2.0 % total strain $f_{y,2.0}$ and the 0.2 %-proof strength $f_{y,0.2}$, (c) the tensile strength f_t and (d) the ratio of yield strength and tensile strength f_y/f_t from post-fire tests on S355J2+N, S690QL and S960QL and values from literature.

3.4 Comparison to literature

In Fig. 4, the reduction factors for material properties from post-fire tests of the present study are compared to values from literature (2-19). The investigated steels of the various references therefore are divided into four groups: mild steels with $f_{y,nom} \leq 460$ N/mm² (129 tests) (2-7, 10), high-strength steels with $f_{y,nom} \leq 700$ N/mm² (111 tests) (3-5, 9, 11-16), ultra-high-strength steels with $f_{y,nom} \leq 960$ N/mm² (69 tests) (15, 18) and ultra-high-strength steels with $f_{y,nom} > 960$ N/mm² (22 tests) (16, 17, 19).

In general, the comparison to literature supports the findings of the present study. In most of the studies, the Young's modulus (Fig. 4(a)) was almost completely reversible in post-fire tests and independent from the initial steel grade. Only few studies (3, 8) on high- and ultra-high-strength steels revealed a slight deterioration of the Young's modulus in cases with high maximum temperatures.

Regarding the yield strength as well as the tensile strength in Fig. 4(b) and (c), the investigated mild steel S355J2+N corresponds to the values of mild steels from literature with a slight strength decrease for maximum temperatures T_u exceeding 550°C. In case of the high- and ultra-high-strength steels a larger scatter of the reduction factors from literature occurs. However, the values of the present study almost represent the mean values of the data from literature. The increased ductility of high-strength steels after very high temperatures is confirmed by the decrease of the ratio of the 0.2 %-proof-strength and the tensile strength. The values from literature overall agree to the ratios from the present study. In general, the ratio is smaller for mild steels at ambient temperature and up to maximum temperatures of $T_u \leq 550^\circ\text{C}$. For higher maximum temperatures, the ratios decrease for high- and ultra-high-strength steels and become similar to the ones of mild steels.

3.5 Post-Fire Microstructure

Fig. 5 shows micrographs of the post-fire test specimens. In case of the mild steel S355J2+N (Fig. 5(a)) a fine-grained ferrite perlite structure is visible at ambient temperature, which was achieved through the initial normalising process. Up to a maximum temperature of $T_u = 700^\circ\text{C}$ this structure is not significantly affected by the elevated temperatures. After an exposure to $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$, lamellar carbide precipitates are visible and the previously existing grid structure with distinct grain borders is less pronounced. The changes in the microstructure are a possible explanation for the slight deterioration of the material properties of S355J2+N after $T_u = 900^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 5 Micrographs of the specimens from post-fire tests on material (a) S355J2+N, (b) S690QL and (c) S960QL.

The microstructure of the initial high-strength steels (Fig. 5(b), (c)) is typical for quenched and tempered steels with a fine-grained structure at ambient temperature. The grain sizes of the structure of steel S960QL in Fig. 5(c) are slightly smaller than those of S690QL in Fig. 5(b). Up to a maximum temperature of $T_u = 550^\circ\text{C}$ the microstructure of both high-strength steels is not significantly changed. Only partly carbide precipitates are visible after $T_u = 550^\circ\text{C}$. After $T_u = 700^\circ\text{C}$, however, in case of the steel S690QL, the structure consists of mostly ferrite phases. The structure of S960QL is also changed compared to the initial state, as the grain sizes are slightly larger and are in the range of the initial

structure of S690QL. The stress-strain-curves from post-fire tests (Fig. 3) also show that the structural material behaviour of the material S960QL after an exposure to $T_u=700^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds to the behaviour of S690QL at ambient temperature. After an exposure to $T_u=900^\circ\text{C}$ both high-strength steels have a coarser grained structure compared to the initial microstructure. The exceeding of the A_1 -phase-change-temperature leads to the transformation of the mostly austenitic microstructure to a mixed structure consisting of ferrite and perlite phases. Further, lamellar carbide precipitates are visible, like in case of the mild steel S355J2+N. The changed microstructures of the high-strength steels after $T_u=900^\circ\text{C}$ hint to the changed mechanical material behaviour, which corresponds to the characteristics of common mild steels (Fig. 3).

4 SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive study on the post-fire mechanical material behaviour of high- and ultra-high-strength steels considering the differences to mild steels has been carried out. The study consisted of post-fire tensile tests on steels of grades S355J2+N, S690QL and S960QL. In addition, existing data from literature was used for a comparative study of the mechanical material properties including strength and stiffness values. The following conclusions were drawn:

- The mechanical material behaviour of mild steels is almost fully reversible up to a maximum temperature of 700°C during heating. Higher maximum temperatures lead to a reduction in strength of about 30 % in case of the yield strength and 20 % in case of the tensile strength.
- The strength recovery of high- and ultra-high-strength steels is strongly dependent on the maximum temperature of the heating phase. Up to a temperature of 550°C reversible material behaviour was observed. However, higher temperatures lead to a significant strength reduction after cooling.
- When the A_1 -phase-change temperature has been exceeded during heating the microstructure of initial high-strength quenched and tempered steels is changed to a coarser grained structure, which leads to reduced strength values in tensile tests.
- The recovery of the Young's modulus is almost independent from material as well as from the maximum temperature. The initial values were nearly achieved after cooling in most cases.
- The post-fire ductility of high- and ultra-high-strength steels is affected by high temperatures. After heating and cooling the ductility of the investigated high-strength materials were increased and comparable to mild steels.

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